

THE PROCEDURE AND REGULATIONS FOR SELECTING AND APPOINTING HEIRS APPARENT IN THE ASHTARKHANID DYNASTY

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ABSTRACT

*In the Ashtarkhanid dynasty, which came to power in Bukhara after the Shaybanids, the process of selecting the heir apparent followed the same principles as those practiced by the Shaybanid rulers of Bukhara: the candidate had to belong to the ruling lineage and be the eldest in age. According to Yusuf Munshi's *Tarikh-i Muqim-khan* ("History of Muqim Khan"), the establishment of this rule was connected with the following event*

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"When Baki Muhammad Khan and Vali Muhammad Khan were defeated by the infidels (referring to the Safavids) and approached Transoxiana, the emirs of Bukhara received news that Din Muhammad Khan had been killed in battle with the Qizilbash. His two brothers reached Transoxiana. Considering this a favorable sign and offering thanks, the emirs of Bukhara went out to welcome the princes and, on the same day, placed the crown upon the head of Baki Muhammad Khan. Vali Muhammad Khan was appointed heir apparent and sent to the province of Balkh, the *qubbat al-Islam* ('Dome of Islam')." ¹

In 1601, political power in the Bukhara Khanate passed to a new dynasty — the descendants of Tuqay Timur, who are most commonly referred to in the sources as the "Jonids" (after Jani Muhammad Khan) or the "Ashtarkhanids" (according to their place of origin). ²

Although Baki Muhammad Khan ruled the Bukhara Khanate until 1605, during the initial phase of his reign, due to established dynastic traditions, his father—Jonibek Sultan, the eldest representative of the lineage—was officially recognized as the Khan of Bukhara in 1601–1603. The Friday sermon (khutbah) was proclaimed in his name, and coins were minted bearing his name. For this reason, the dynasty was initially referred to as the "Jonids," that is, named after Jonibek Sultan. However, although Jonibek Sultan was formally acknowledged as khan until his death in December 1603, the actual authority and control over governance rested entirely in the hands of Baki Muhammad Khan. ³

¹ Мухаммед Юсуф Мунши. Муқим-ханская история. Перевод с таджикского, предисловие, примечания и указатели профессора Семёнов А.А.- Ташкент: Издательство Академии наук Узбекской ССР, 1956. - С 74-75; Ahmedov B. *Tarixdan saboqlar*. T.: O'qituvchi, 1994. 185-b.

² Zamonov A., Subhonov F. *Buxoroning ashtarxoniy hukmdorlari*. – T.: Bayoz, 2021. – B. 21.

³ Zamonov A., Subhonov F. *Buxoroning ashtarxoniy hukmdorlari*. – T.: Bayoz, 2021. – B. 25.

In the early Ashtarkhanid period, the throne did not pass from father to son but from elder brother to younger. After the death of Baki Muhammad Khan, his brother, Vali Muhammad Khan—who had previously been proclaimed heir—ascended the throne. However, once the court officials recognized Vali Muhammad Khan's unsuitability for rulership, they decided to replace him in the interest of the country's peace and prosperity. According to their decision, in 1609 the throne was to be given to Vali Muhammad Khan's nephew, Imamquli Khan, the eldest son of the late Din Muhammad Khan, since he was the senior member of the dynasty by age (born in 1589).

Taking advantage of Vali Muhammad Khan's absence—he had gone hunting to Qarshi—the officials enthroned Imamquli Khan and began preparing for military action to secure his authority. The new khan received reinforcement from Badakhshan, where his brother Nadr Muhammad joined him. Learning of the situation, Vali Muhammad Khan set out with his two sons to the court of Shah Abbas of Iran. With Abbas's support he returned, but in the battle near Samarkand in 1611, he was defeated by Imamquli Khan and executed.⁴

Thus, following these events, Imamquli Khan formally ascended the throne of the Bukhara Khanate in 1611. His brother, Nadr Muhammad Khan, was appointed governor of Balkh and designated heir apparent. Although Imamquli Khan had three sons — Iskandar Sultan, Pir Muhammad Sultan (Muhammad Ali), and Bahram Sultan — he adhered to the established tradition and designated his brother, Nadr Muhammad Khan, as successor to the throne.⁵

Nadr Muhammad ibn Din Muhammad ibn Jonibek Sultan was born in 1592/1593. On his mother's side, Nadr Muhammad's lineage traces back to the *sayyids*, the descendants of the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him). Numerous historical sources preserve reliable accounts of this. In particular, the work *Tarikh-i Muqimkhani* records the following event:

"During the conquest of Mashhad, the Shaybanid ruler Abdulmumin Khan carried out extensive massacres (these events occurred in the late 1580s, during the reign of Abdullah Khan). In this city resided members of the household of the *sayyids*, descendants of Imam Ali Musa Riza. Upon hearing of the situation, they approached Din Muhammad, saying: 'I have a daughter. If you save me and my family from this slaughter, I will give her to you in marriage.' Following Din Muhammad's intervention, the household of Imam Ali Musa Riza was spared from calamity. Remaining true to his word, the descendant of Imam Ali gave his daughter, Shahribonu Begim, in marriage to Din Muhammad."⁶

Thus, the Ashtarkhanid ruler of Bukhara, Din Muhammad Khan, married the daughter of Mirzo Sayyid Abu Talib, and from this union their son Nadr Muhammad Khan was born. Consequently, his descendants came to possess the status of *sayyids*, that is, the title of the descendants of the Prophet.⁷

Thus, when Nadr Muhammad Khan and his descendants ascended the throne of the Bukhara Khanate, they regarded themselves as legitimate from two perspectives: in accordance with Chinggisid dynastic customs, and through the Islamic recognition of their lineage. Consequently, they adopted the practice of placing the word *sayyid* before their names.

⁴ Мухаммед Юсуф Мунши. Муким-ханская история. Перевод с таджикского, предисловие, примечания и указатели профессора Семёнов А.А. - Ташкент:издательство академии наук Узбекской ССР, 1956. - С. 70-71.

⁵ Алексеев А.К. Политическая история Тукай-Тимуридов. - С.-Петербург: С.-Петербургского Университета 2006. – С 159.

⁶ Мухаммед Юсуф Мунши. Муким-ханская история. Перевод с таджикского, предисловие, примечания и указатели профессора Семёнов А.А. – Т.: Издательство Академии наук Узбекской ССР, 1956. – С . 98-99.

⁷ Аминов Б. Марказий Мовароуннахр кабртош битиклари ва улардаги тарихий шахслар генеалогияси (ХВ-XX асрлар). Н.: Баёз, 2021. – Б. 79.

According to historical sources, Nadr Muhammad Khan had more than ten heirs. As a result of an uprising that broke out in the country, he was deposed from the throne, and his eldest son, Abdulaziz Khan, was installed in his place. This event can be compared to the earlier transfer of power from Vali Muhammad Khan to Imamquli Khan. Under his father's supervision, Abdulaziz Khan began governing the province of Khuttalon in 1626 and between 1630 and 1642 administered the western districts of Balkh.⁸

In 1642, after Imamquli Khan abdicated in favor of his brother Nadr Muhammad Khan, the new ruler granted the administration of all regions of the state to his sons as *suyurghal* fiefs. Within this distribution, Abdulaziz Khan was appointed governor of Samarkand, one of the central regions of the khanate.

There were several reasons that justified Abdulaziz's accession to the throne. First, he was the eldest son.⁹

This aligned with the prevailing dynastic custom whereby the throne was assumed by the eldest member of the ruling lineage. Second, like his father, his genealogy traced back to the *sayyids* (the Juybar Khojas). The support for his enthronement by Khoja Tajiddin of the Juybar Khojas was motivated by their intention to further strengthen the political influence of the Juybariyya.¹⁰

Third, Nadr Muhammad Khan did not achieve the same level of success in governing the state as his brother had. This contributed to the onset of fragmentation within the khanate. Consequently, a carefully orchestrated conspiracy was prepared against Nadr Muhammad Khan, leading to his overthrow and the enthronement of his son.

⁸ Султонов Ф., Бозорбоев Ф. Ўзбекистон ҳукмдорлари. Т.: Алишер Навоий номидаги Ўзбекистон Миллий кутубхонаси, 2007. – Б. 49.

⁹ Азамат Зиё. Ўзбек давлатчилик тарихи. – Б.264.

¹⁰ Арминий Вамбери. Бухоро ёхуд Мовароуннахр тарихи. 2-жилд. Т.: Info capital group, 2019. – Б. 128.